

ANALYSIS OF ARTEFACT - TEXTBOOK

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Abstract:

In this paper I am going to write about the artefact 'textbook'. I think textbook plays most important role in any education system or education domain. We can also say that it is heart of education. Some place where the instruction material is not available then the role of textbook is very important. Generally textbook is made for the student and to suitable to their age group. It also covers the contents which are given in the syllabus. In this paper I will also try to discuss about the role of textbook in the curriculum and how it is helpful to achieve the objectives of school curriculum and the teaching learning process and I will also try to draw attention towards the drawbacks of the textbook.

Key Words: Artefact, Dropout, Pushout & Teaching Learning Material

Textbook is most important tool of the teaching learning process through which we can determine what will be taught and how should be taught. In the modern era, we can see there are many things like internet, television, computer etc. which are trying to get the position or place of textbook but textbook remain highly knowledgeable source in school. Among many teaching learning material and instruments the textbook is one of the cheapest thing. *"With some variation in different subjects and at different levels, the textbook is used for class routines like loud reading, silent reading, comprehension exercises, recapitulation, homework, and tests. At all levels of school education, the textbook acts as a substitute syllabus or rather as the operative part of the syllabus"* (Krishna Kumar, 1986)

Definition of Textbook:

There are many ways to define the textbook but main and important thing of the textbook is that it is an instrument of instructions that facilitates the teaching learning process. The process in which all the major components and ideals of syllabus prescribed and summarized. They are also organized very logically and suitable to child psychology. Sometimes a textbook is called 'the teacher in print'

Webster's Dictionary:

"A text-book is any manual of instruction, a book containing a presentation of the principles of the subject used as a basis of instruction."

Encyclopedia of Educational Research (Third Edition):

In the modern sense and as "commonly understood; the textbook is a learning instrument usually employed in schools and colleges to support aerogramme of instruction. In ordinary usage the textbook is printed, it is on-consumable, it is hard bound, it serves as an avowed instructional purpose, and it is placed in the hands of learner."

Importance of Textbook:

In J. R. Melton's paper, he talks about the textbook importance and the role of the textbook (1) *Textbooks have survived several decades of conspicuous educational change and still retain a high rank as essential instructional material.* (2) *By and large, it is likely that they contribute to better teaching than there would be without them.* (3) *Desirable results from using textbooks in schools depend upon the qualities of the particular book used and upon how it is used.* (Melton, 1953)

To help to Teacher:

Textbook is very helpful tool for teacher. It provides useful guidance to plan the lesson day to day. It is also helpful when teacher is teaching during the process he uses the references or give the references from the textbook. Many time the textbook suggest assignments and the activities to be taken during teaching learning process.

To Help the Student:

One of the most important aspects for student as well as teacher, sometimes or we can say that many times it gives pleasure to teacher and student. Textbook is very easily available tools to prepare for examination as well as for assignments. It also helpful to revise what the student learnt in classroom. The textbook is all time friend of student. Therefore, it is very important tool for student.

To Self-Study:

Sometime a teacher who is not experienced or mature. She is not trained in a position to clear whole topic or go into the depth of that topic then the text book plays very vital role for students to do self-study. I experienced these things, when I was doing masters in English literature most of the study material or notes I made from textbook because sometime professors were not interested to teach the syllabus, sometime it is very difficult for new professor to teach us. Then we learnt from the textbook.

I have another experience, one of my friend doing his B.A. from an open university in Maharashtra (YCMOU) I read his many of textbooks. I felt like someone is teaching to me and I am learning. The textbooks were very easy to understand and easy to self-study.

Uniformity Among the Students:

I think Uniformity among the students is one of the major factor of the textbook. In all the schools which are following the same board curriculum, the uniformity comes automatically among the students they learn same textbook whether they come from different socio economic background or from different castes. Their learning might be different but the learning process is same for them.

I can also say that the text book provides the common ground to teacher and students they may explore new things together.

Drawbacks of Text Books:

There are many critics and the drawbacks of textbooks also. While discussion with my classmates and other friends they critic that the textbook can't replace natural learning for students. They said that the without textbook we can teach to child whatever we want children need to feel free and learn practically. I agree with above things because I saw a documentary of "development through education" which is totally based on science. In Maharashtra near to Pune there is a school (established by Kalbag more than 20 years ago) in which they are teaching only practical knowledge through this the students are learning all the things. (Which I understood).

In an interview Prof. Anil Sadgopal used a new term for the dropout students. They said that they are not "drop outs" they are "pushed outs" by the government. Because the students can't handle the burden of heavy textbooks.

Apart from that there are many other drawbacks like sometimes children find the textbook material better than the teacher or his teaching and the explanation then they don't show the regard to teacher. Some time teaching and learning become rigid because teacher has to teach whatever is given in the textbook as it is. I can say that the textbooks give only bookish knowledge and the practical reality is different sometime. Because we can't find the situation same which is given in the textbook. In APU we are learning how the education developed a human (in textbooks, theories) but when I went to field immersion a man asked me why I should educate my child in school, I will teach him which is required to sustain through agriculture. There is no need of education.

Sometime textbooks appose to adopt new methodology of teaching learning in fact sometimes they are not suitable to progressive methods.

Conclusion:

Based on above discussion we can say that there are both the things. Importance and the drawbacks of textbook. As usually many things have both sides like textbook but textbook supposed to a very important part of the education system. It is very helpful when we don't have other materials to teach. I would like to conclude this paper with the words of Gandhi which are opposing to textbook-

"If textbooks are treated as a vehicle for education, the living word of the teacher has very little value. A teacher who teaches from textbooks does not impart originality to his pupils. He himself becomes a slave of text-books and has no opportunity or occasion to be original. It therefore seems that the less textbooks there are the better it is for the teacher and his pupils." (Gandhi, 1939 from Krishna Kumar's paper)

References:

1. Ahemad, S. (2015, May 09). Retrieved from Scibed : file:///c:/users/student/downloads/importance%20of%20textbook.html
2. Butt, D. L. (2015). The role of textbooks: an assessment issue? Geographical Association, 202-203.
3. George Greisen Mallinson, H. E. (2015). The Reading Difficulty of Textbooks in Elementary Science. Chicago Journal, 460-463.
4. Heyneman, S. (2006). The role of textbooks in a Modern Syatem of Education: Towards High Quality Education for all. Vanderbilt University.
5. Kumar, K. (2011). Textbooks and Educational Culture. Economic and Political Weekly, 1309-1311.
6. Melton, J. R. (2015). Using Textbooks Wisely. The University of North Carolina PRESS, 138-44.
7. Stodolsky, L. A. (2015). Teachers and Textbooks: Materials Use in Four Fourth-Grade Classrooms. Chicago Journal, 249-275.
8. Webster's Dictionary
9. Encyclopedia of Educational Research (Third Edition)